

ADVANCED MATERIALS

Supporting Information

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In Situ Carbon Corrosion and Cu Leaching as a Strategy for Boosting Oxygen Evolution Reaction in Multimetal Electrocatalysts

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Experimental Section

Chemicals and materials: Cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), iron(III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), copper(II) nitrate hemi(pentahydrate) ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), ruthenium(IV)-oxide (RuO_2), iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), absolute ethanol, Nafion® 117 ~ 5%, N-Boc-ethylenediamine, lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4), and hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) were from Sigma-Aldrich. Potassium hydroxide was from J. T. Baker. The quartz capillaries with an outer diameter of 1.2 mm / inner diameter of 0.9 mm with a total length of 7.5 cm were from Science Products. Nickel foam was from Goodfellow. All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

Preparation of materials:

Catalyst preparation: CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) was synthesized by a one-step hydrothermal reaction. $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0218 g, 0.075 mmol), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0218 g, 0.075 mmol), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0303 g, 0.075 mmol), $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01745 g, 0.0375 mmol) and HMT (0.0315 g, 0.225 mmol) were mixed in 15 ml absolute ethanol. The solution was ultrasonicated for 30 min, and then transferred to a 50 ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave. After sealing, the autoclave was placed in an oven at 180 °C for 12 h and then

cooled down in ambient conditions. The product was collected by centrifugation and several times washed with deionized water and ethanol, and then finally dried in an oven at 70°C. For comparison other catalysts like Fe, CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1.5) were synthesized analogously by only changing the ratio of each metal salt.

Carbon nanoelectrode (CNEs) fabrication: The fabrication of CNEs followed our previously reported work.^[1-3] CNEs were fabricated using laser-pulled quartz capillaries followed by a pyrolysis process using a mixed propane / butane gas as carbon source. Focused ion beam (FIB) milling of the as-prepared CNEs led to CNEs with defined disk diameter and smooth carbon surface.

CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)@CNE nanoassembly preparation: Immobilisation of single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particles on nanoelectrodes was performed following a strategy as recently reported.^[2] To improve the connection between the single catalyst particle and the CNE, electrografting of N-Boc-ethylenediamine was performed to modify the CNE surface. The catalyst particles were drop-coated onto an ultra-flat gold-modified wafer, from which individual particles could be selected under SEM control, picked up with the micromanipulator, and then placed on the tip of the CNE.

Instruments and material characterizations: The quartz capillaries were pulled using a P-2000 laser puller (Sutter Instrument) using the pulling parameters: HEAT = 740, FILAMENT = 4, VELOCITY = 45, DELAY = 130, and PULL = 100. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained using a Quanta 3D FEG scanning electron microscope (FEI) operated at 30.0 kV in the high-vacuum mode. Electrostatic charging of the CNEs was prevented by inserting a Cu wire from the back end of the capillary, which is essential for an effective FIB milling process. FIB milling of the as-prepared CNEs was performed using the same Quanta 3D ESEM, which is equipped with a Ga-FIB source. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

measurements were performed using a Bruker D8 Discover X-ray diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) in the range $2\theta = 5\sim 80^\circ$. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images, scanning TEM images, high-resolution TEM images, and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping were obtained using a JEOL microscope (JEM-2800) with a Schottky-type emission source working at 200 kV. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out with an AXIS Nova spectrometer (Kratos Analytical) equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1487 eV, 15 mA emission current), maintaining a chamber pressure of $\approx 2 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar. The high-resolution spectra of the core levels were collected in the fixed transmission mode at a pass energy of 20 eV. Charging effects were compensated using a flood gun during spectra acquisition. The C 1s peak of adventitious carbon at 284.8 eV was used for calibration of the binding energies. The element content was investigated by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). For elemental post-analysis of the catalysts after electrochemical testing, samples were drop-coated on a rotating disc electrode (RDE) and scratched off from the electrode surface after electrochemical tests. Gas chromatography measurements were conducted using a SRI-8610C GC equipped with a packed 3 m HaySep D column and a thermal conductivity detector. The equipment was previously calibrated with several dilutions of known O $_2$ concentrations. Raman spectra were obtained using a Jubin-Yvoni HR550 spectrometer (HORIBA) equipped with a laser source of $\lambda = 532 \text{ nm}$ (Ventus 532, Laser Quantum). The measurements were conducted using a laser power of 2 mW, a grating of 1800 grooves mm^{-1} , and a 60x magnification immersible objective.

Electrochemical measurements: All electrochemical measurements were performed in a conventional three-electrode configuration using an Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat/galvanostat (Metrohm). A polished glassy carbon electrode with a geometric area of 0.1256 cm^2 was used as the working electrode, a cylindrical platinum mesh as the counter electrode,

which was kept in a compartment separated by means of a glass frit during the measurements to avoid contamination of the working electrode with potentially dissolved Pt, and a double junction Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl as the reference electrode. The KOH electrolyte was purified with chelating ion exchange resin (Chelex 100, Bio-Rad) before use to avoid contamination by metal impurities. All measured potentials in 1M KOH were converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), according to the equation:

$$E_{RHE} = E_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.207 + 0.059 \cdot pH.$$

Catalyst inks were prepared by dispersing the catalyst powder (5 mg) in a mixture of ethanol (980 μ l) and 5 % Nafion (20 μ l) followed by ultrasonication for 30 min. A defined ink volume was pipetted onto the pre-cleaned glassy carbon electrode to form a catalyst film loading of 0.5 mg cm⁻². The resulting films were left to dry in the air under ambient conditions for at least 20 min. Cyclic voltammograms (CVs) were recorded in the potential range from 0 to 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl at a scan rate of 10 mV·s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was recorded at the open circuit potential (OCP) of the electrode, using an ac perturbation of 10 mV_{pp} in the frequency range from 50 kHz to 1 Hz. The uncompensated resistance R_u , was determined from the corresponding Nyquist plot and later used for ohmic drop correction according to $E_c = E_m - iR_u$, where E_c is the corrected potential and E_m is the measured potential. The OER activity was recorded by linear sweep voltammetry in the potential range from 0 V to 0.7 V vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ in 1 M purified KOH at an electrode rotation of 1600 rpm. The long-term performance of the catalysts was evaluated by chronopotentiometry in 1 M KOH (room temperature) at a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² and a rotation speed of 1600 rpm. The long-term performance at higher current densities was evaluated using Ni foam (0.5*0.5 cm²) as the base electrode material, considering the higher corrosion resistance compared to carbon-based electrodes in alkaline electrolytes. The catalysts ink was drop-coated on NF with a loading equivalent to 0.5 mg·cm⁻² and exposed to

the electrolyte at current densities from 100 to 500 mA·cm⁻² to obtain stability performance at high current densities in 1 M KOH (room temperature). The stability performance under close to industrial conditions (7 M KOH and at 50 °C) was also investigated both in a stationary cell (100 mA·cm⁻²) and a flow-through electrolyzer (500 mA·cm⁻²). The amount of O₂ was detected by means of gas chromatography (SRI-8610C). During the measurement, N₂ was constantly purged into the electrolyte at a flow rate of 9 mL·min⁻¹ adjusted by a mass flow controller (AALBORG) to transport the produced O₂ into the GC. The Faradaic efficiency (FE) of O₂ was calculated using the equation:

$$FE_{O_2} = \frac{ne_{O_2}^- \times x_{O_2} \times \text{flow } N_2 \times F}{i_{\text{total}} \times 1,000,000 \times R} \times 100\%$$

where $ne_{O_2}^-$ is the number of electrons involved in the OER, x_{O_2} is the amount detected by the GC in ppm, the flow of N₂ in L·s⁻¹, $F = 96486$ is the Faraday constant in A*s·mol⁻¹, i_{total} is the measured current in A and $R = 26.517$ the molar volume in L·mol⁻¹.

Tafel slopes were determined from the slope of plots of overpotential against current in accordance with the Tafel equation:

$$\eta = a + b \log j$$

where η (mV) denotes the applied overpotential, j (A·cm⁻²) is the current density, b (mV·dec⁻¹) represents the Tafel slope.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded at various scan rates (10, 20, 30, 40, 50 mV·s⁻¹) to derive the double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}). The C_{dl} was determined by plotting $\Delta J = (J_a - J_c)/2$ against the scan rate, where J_a and J_c are the anodic and cathodic current densities, respectively.

Figure S1. a-d) High resolution SEM images of CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) obtained in TEM.

Figure S2. a-d) Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5). Insets show the ICP-MS determined molar ratio of the constituting metals.

Figure S3. a) High-resolution SEM images of a single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particle on a carbon nanoelectrode. b) Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping (carbon) of the same single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particle on carbon nanoelectrode. c) EDX line scan (carbon) of a single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5).

Figure S4. XRD patterns of CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5).

Figure S5. High-resolution TEM images of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5).

Figure S6. XPS spectra of (a) Co 2p, (b) Ni 2p, (d) Cu 2p, (e) N 1s, (f) O 1s in CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5). (c) XPS survey spectra of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), CoNiFe (1:1:1); CoNiCu (1:1:1); CoNi(1:1).

Figure S7. a) XPS spectra of single Fe material. b) Raman spectra of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) and pure Fe_2O_3 .

Figure S8. Bar graph of the overpotential at a current density of 10 mA·cm⁻² for CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) and RuO₂. Average obtained from three independent experiment.

Figure S9. Cyclic voltammograms (CV) for the determination of the double-layer capacitance of different samples and the corresponding plots of the charge current densities against CV scan rates. a) CoNi (1:1), b) CoNiCu (1:1:1), c) CoNiFe (1:1:1), d) CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), e) CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1), f) CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), g) RuO₂, h) Bare RDE(GC).

Figure S10. Tafel slopes of CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) and RuO₂.

Figure S11. a) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) polarization curves of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1.5). b) Bar graph of the overpotential at a current density of $10 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ for CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1.5). Average obtained from three independent experiment. c) Double layer capacitance normalized LSVs of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1.5). d) Tafel slopes of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:1.5).

Figure S12. Plots showing the change of OER overpotential (at $10 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$) with CV cycle number. Average obtained from three independent experiment.

Figure S13. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) polarization curves after different numbers of CV cycles (8, 16, 24, 32). a) CoNi (1:1). b) CoNiCu (1:1:1). c) CoNiFe (1:1:1). d) CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5).

Figure S14. Chronopotentiometric stability test of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) on Ni foam at $100 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in 1 M KOH. Inset shows the LSVs of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) on Ni foam before and after the 25 h stability test. Current densities were normalized by geometric area of NF.

Figure S15. Chronopotentiometric stability test of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) on Ni foam at different current densities ($100 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, $300 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, and $500 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). The inset shows the LSVs of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) on Ni foam after stability test at different current densities. Current densities were normalized by geometric area of NF.

Figure S16. Photograph of the electrochemical flow-through electrolyzer system with a water bath to adjust the temperature.

Figure S17. a-c) Amount of O₂ and Faradaic efficiency vs time during chronopotentiometry of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) at 100 mA·cm⁻², 200 mA·cm⁻², and 300 mA·cm⁻² in 1 M KOH at 25 °C. d-g) Amount of O₂ and Faradaic efficiency vs time for CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) at 100 mA·cm⁻², 200 mA·cm⁻², and 300 mA·cm⁻² in 7 M KOH at 50 °C. h) Average Faradaic efficiency and stability of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) at 100 mA·cm⁻², 200 mA·cm⁻², and 300 mA·cm⁻² in 7 M KOH at 50 °C. Current densities were normalized by geometric area of NF

Figure S18. XPS determination of the chemical surface states of Ni 2p (a) and Co 2p (b) for CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1), CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) catalysts.

Figure S19. Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) before, after 32 CVs, and after 2000 CVs (The CVs were conducted between 1.2 V and 1.7 V vs RHE at a scan rate of $100 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$).

Figure S20. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) after a) 32 and b) 2,000 CVs.

Figure S21. a) XPS survey spectra of CoNi (1:1) and CoNi (1:1) after the activation process. b) XPS survey spectra of CoNiCu (1:1:1) and CoNiCu (1:1:1) after the activation process. c) XPS survey spectra of CoNiFe (1:1:1) and CoNiFe (1:1:1) after the activation process. d) XPS survey spectra of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) after the activation process.

Figure S22. a,b) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) and the corresponding size distribution.

Figure S23. a,b) Carbon nanoelectrode before and after Focus ion beam (FIB) milling process.

Figure S24. a) STEM-DF images of a single particle (CoNiFeCu(1:1:1:0.5)) on a carbon nanoelectrode (without surface functionalization). b) STEM image of the single particle (CoNiFeCu(1:1:1:0.5)) on a carbon nanoelectrode after 5 CV cycles.

Figure S25. a,b) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of single particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) on CNE-1 and CNE-2. c,d) High-resolution SEM images of single particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) on CNE-1 and CNE-2 obtained in the TEM.

Figure S26. a,b) Cyclic voltammograms of single particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) on CNE-1 and CNE-2 in 1 M KOH. c) 5th CV of single particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) on CNE-1, CNE-2, and bare CNE. d) 5th CV of single particles (CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)) on CNE-1, CNE-2, and bare CNE normalized by the geometric area.

Figure S27. a-c) TEM images of a single particle (CoNiFeCu(1:1:1:0.5)) on a carbon nanoelectrode before electrochemical experiments. d-f) TEM images of the same particle as in a-c) on a carbon nanoelectrode after 5 CVs. g-i) TEM images of the same particle on a carbon nanoelectrode after 15 CVs.

Figure S28. Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping of a single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particle on the carbon nanoelectrode before the activation CVs (a), after 5 CVs (b), and after 15 CVs (c). The detected Fe in the nanoelectrode can be from Fe contamination during carbon nanoelectrode preparation.

Figure S29. a-c) Mixed energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping of a single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particle on a nanoelectrode before the electrochemical experiments, after 5 CVs, and after 15 CVs. d-f) EDX line scan across the single CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) particle before the electrochemical experiments, after 5 CVs, and after 15 CVs.

Figure S30. a-d) Tafel slopes of CoNi (1:1), CoNiCu (1:1:1), CoNiFe (1:1:1) and CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) after different numbers of CVs.

Figure S31. Cyclic voltammograms after different cycle numbers. a) CoNi (1:1); b) CoNiCu (1:1:1); c) CoNiFe (1:1:1); d) CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5).

Table S1. Comparisons of the electrocatalytic performance of CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5) and some recently reported representative OER catalysts.

Electrocatalysts	Substrate	Electrolyte	η (mV vs. RHE)@10 mA \cdot cm ⁻²	Tafel slope(m V \cdot dec ⁻¹)	Ref.
CoNiFeCu (1:1:1:0.5)	Glassy carbon	Purified 1M KOH	291.5 \pm 0.5mV	43.9	This work
CoNi-SAs/NC	Carbon cloth	1M KOH	340 mV	58.7	<i>Adv. Mater.</i> , 2019 , 31, 1905622 ^[4]
NiCo LDH-TPA	Graphene foam	1M KOH	265 mV	52.4	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> , 2021 , 60, 10614–10619 ^[5]
Co-Mo-P/CoNWs	Ni foam	1M KOH	270 mV	116	<i>Adv. Funct. Mater.</i> , 2020 , 30, 2002533 ^[6]
NiCoP/C	Glassy carbon	1M KOH	330 mV	96	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> , 2017 , 56, 3897–3900. ^[7]
Co ₃ O ₄ /Co-Fe	Glassy carbon	1M KOH	297 mV	61	<i>Adv. Mater.</i> , 2018 ,30, 1801211. ^[8]
Zn _{0.4} Ni _{0.6} Co ₂ O ₄ /NCNTs	Glassy carbon	0.1 M KOH	410 mV	118.3	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2020 , 59, 6492–6499 ^[9]
Cs _{0.4} La _{0.6} Mn _{0.25} C _{0.75} O ₃	Glassy carbon	1M KOH	374 mV	101	<i>Nat. Commun.</i> 2020 , 11, 3513 ^[10]
CoFe-CDs	Glassy carbon	1 M KOH	320 mV	84.9	<i>Appl. Catal., B</i> 2020 , 267, 118657 ^[11]
NiCoP-5%	Glassy carbon	1 M KOH	290 mV	66	<i>Nano Lett.</i> 2021 , 21, 823–832 ^[12]
NiCo ^{III} Fe-LDH/N-GO	Glassy carbon	0.1 M KOH	310 mV	56.8	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2018 , 8, 1701905 ^[13]
NiCo _{2-x} Fe _x O ₄ NBs	Carbon paper	1M KOH	274 mV	42	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2021 , 60, 11841–11846 ^[14]
NiFeCr/NF	Ni foam	1 M KOH	\approx 270 mV	36	<i>Energy Environ. Sci.</i> 2020 , 13, 4225–4237 ^[15]
K(MgMnFeCoNi)F ₃	Glassy carbon	1 M KOH	314 mV	55	<i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i> 2020 , 142, 4550–4554 ^[16]

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